
ANALYSIS OF MIGRATION FROM DEVELOPING COUNTRIES

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Abstract

In this study, I seek to investigate the causes, motives, major developing countries of origin of international migrants, and the countries that these migrants choose to move to. Several previous studies were analyzed, and information gathered about the reasons and motivations, destinations, and consequences of migration. For the secondary study, I used information from the 10 most populous developing nations as well as the destinations of those migrants. The World Bank and the World Migration Report published in 2022 were used to gather all information. According to research, immigrants from developing nations choose to move to the US, and the majority of Indians leave their country in order to enhance their standard of living. Mexico sends the most emigrants to the United States.

Introduction

The movement of people within a country or across an international border to change their place of residence is called migration. International migrants have a great effect on the economies of countries, and such migration may have different causes, goals, directions, and consequences. According to the National Geographic Society, international migrants are divided into three types: immigrants, emigrants, and refugees. Immigrants are people who come to a country to create a new home. Emigrants are people who quit their country and to another one. Refugees are a bunch of people who leave their country because of various problems in their former country. The overall number of displaced people in 2019 amounted to 84.4 million, and almost three-quarters of all migrants (73 percentile) derive from developing countries, according to the IOM's World Migration Report 2022. The purpose of this paper is to analyze the causes, most-traveled destinations, and consequences of migration from developing countries.

Reasons and motivations for migration

People move for a variety of reasons, and one dichotomy that comes up frequently is migration between unforced and voluntarily. It is difficult to draw a

clear distinction between forced migration and voluntary migration, according to Seigel (2020), because there are frequently several reasons why individuals migrate, many of which overlap. From a more forced perspective, we can think of things like conflict, violence, war, persecution, and environmental factors, but there are many other factors or reasons why people migrate. It might be things like access to services for family reasons, which could be both family reunification and family formation. Education or student migrants are also some of the reasons why people migrate. International students increased from 2 million in 2000 to nearly 6.3 million in 2020. (UIS, 2022). According to information now available, seven nations – the United States of America, the United Kingdom, Australia, Germany, Canada, France, and China – were home to over half of these students who were engaged in educational programs. Additionally, there is retirement migration, so people decide to move upon retirement, maybe to a country that is a bit warmer or where their money goes further. The structural elements that have contributed in the development of "conventional" IRM (such as that from Northern to Southern Europe) are well-known from the literature in addition to the "lifestyle" approach (King, Cela, and Fokkema, 2021). On the one hand, they entail demographic aging and rising life expectancy, and on the other, they involve continued personal wealth creation. And of course, there is migration in search of work or employment, and it can be all sorts of people, so it's not only poor people traveling the world in search of jumps, but also, for example, highly skilled people. So, migration in search of work is one of the main reasons people move in search of workers, and it also covers a extensive range of different types of people. According to the International Labor Organization's most recent estimates, there are now 169 million international migrant workers in the world, an increase of 3% since 2017 (ILO, 2021).

Most going destinations of migrants

Europe and Asia have the biggest number of international migrants, according to a report from the International Organization of Migration (2022). In 2020, 86.7 million foreign-born residents were anticipated in Europe, followed by 85.6 million in Asia. Since 2005, these two locations have seen a steady rise in the number of foreign migrants residing there, according to the IOM. The main reasons people migrate to Europe are higher salaries, better job prospects, a higher standard of living, and access to education. Since the 1990s, Europe has experienced a significant influx of immigrants, primarily from Romania, Poland, and Bulgaria, as well as from Africa and Asia. Moreover, according to Hager (2021), both developed and underdeveloped Muslim countries in the Middle East do not want immigrants

to interfere with their way of life. Hence, they convinced European countries to "sponsor" these immigrants so they could receive oil subsidies, and European countries were foolish enough to fall for it. The United States will outperform the rest of the globe on this metric, with close to 51 million migrants in 2020. With around 15.8 million migrants, Germany is home to the second largest such community. Most foreign migrants do not typically reside in the nations where they make up the largest percentage of the population. In contrast to 24 other nations or territories with populations of at least 1 million, the United States has more migrants from all over the world than any other country, but they only make up roughly 15.1% of the country's overall population (Natarajan, Moslimani, and Lopez, 2022). According to Gogol (2022), a lot of people choose to go to the United States and drastically change their lives. Since the regulations were modified in 1968, family reunion was one of the main factors influencing immigration to the United States.

Consequences of migration

Migration is a settlement that affects the well-being of households, the society, and, ultimately, the entire economy in different manners (Natarajan, Moslimani, and Lopez, 2022). The effects of international migration on the welfare of the country of origin are often, though not always, significant and constructive. The leading ways through which external migration reduces poverty level, are increasing income from remittances, the capacity to flat consumption, creating and improving access to finance to start new businesses which leads to increase of new job opportunities, and the utilization of information and assets made available by the international migrant diaspora group. In addition to the net monetary gain, migration and remittances can increase investment in healthcare and education level. Nevertheless, not all effects are good: it is apparently common for migrants to be used by dishonest recruiters or employers; family separation may be difficult for migrants; and extensive immigration can seriously threaten national identity and sovereignty. While though movement has effects on the economies, societies, and cultures of both sending and receiving nations, remittances that migrants send home may be the most tangible and uncontested relationship between migration and development (Engler, 2020). Remittances are usually primarily sent from high-income nations. With a total income of \$68 billion in 2020, the US will continue to lead the world in remittance sending, trailed by the United Arab Emirates \$43.2 billion, as a source of remittances Saudi Arabia has sent \$34.6 billion, and Switzerland and Germany have sent remittances in the amounts of \$27.96 billion and \$22 billion, respectively (World Bank, 2022).

Material and Methods

As secondary data for analysis on migration, I decided to use data from the World Bank website on the top 10 developing countries from which people migrate and the top 10 countries where people prefer to move. The top countries have been identified from the World Migration Report (2022), which is released every year by the International Organization of Migration after careful analysis.

With a contemporary population of almost 7.74 billion, the number of developing nations equals to 152 as illustrated by the IMF. This represents a significant proportion of the world's population, 85.43 percent (WorldData, 2020). The type of data I decided to use is cross-sectional and taken from the top 10 home countries of international migrants worldwide. These countries are India, Mexico, the Russian Federation, the Syrian Arab Republic, China, Bangladesh, Pakistan, Ukraine, the Philippines, and Afghanistan. International migrants who were born in these countries at the end of 2020 will total 115 million.

Since 1970, the United States has been the primary country for immigration from abroad. Since then, the number of citizens who were born abroad increased by four times, rising from 12 million in 1970 to more than 51 million in 2019. Being the second-most popular location for immigrants, Population of Germany has seen the rise over time, from 8.9 million in 2000 to around 16 million in 2020 (IOM, 2022). Besides the United States and Germany, people prefer to migrate to Saudi Arabia, the Russian Federation, the United Kingdom, France, the United Arab Emirates, Canada, Australia, and Spain.

It was decided to create tables and charts for visualization since the goal of this essay is to investigate migration from developing nations. The information on people migrating in 2020 was added to Excel, and a pie chart was created to display the ratio. Another pie chart was created to show the proportion of individuals who choose where to migrate by transferring the data on people who migrated to the top 10 nations in 2020 from the world migration report. A table was also created to highlight the number of people that migrate to each country as their primary destination from each of these immigrants' home nations.

Results

To begin with, as we took the 10 biggest countries that are home-countries for international migrants, the overall number of emigrants from these countries is 67 million. This sample covers 24% of the global migrant population of 281 million.

Figure 1. Proportion of the top 10 countries that are home countries for migrants.

It is clear from Figure 1 that India and Mexico share the highest percentile of emigrants at 17% and 16%, respectively. The reason for this number of migrants is that India has the second largest population, and most Indians migrate to developed countries for good jobs, a good standard of living, education, and medical benefits (Sharma, 2022).

Figure 2. Countries where migrants from developing countries choose to resettle.

Figure 2 shows the proportion of countries to which migrants from developing countries have moved. It is obvious that 28 percent of migrants from developing countries prefer to move to the US. It can be explained that the US is still a country of opportunity and continues to be one of the top preferred destinations for international emigration. The US created one of the highest standards of living in the world, fantastic job prospects and an unrivaled lifestyle.

Table 1.

Column1	US	Saudi Arabia	UAE	Turkey	Ukraine	India	Russia	Pakistan	Kazakistan	Iran	Germany	Other	Total
India	2 723 764	2 502 337	3 171 300	-	-	-	-	1 597 134	-	-	-	1 375 667	11 370 202
Mexico	10 853 105	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	20 266	166 506	11 039 877
Russian Federation	-	-	-	-	3 330 586	-	-	-	2 476 018	-	1 198 831	1 543 528	8 548 963
Syrian Arab Republic	-	823 261	-	3 792 505	-	-	-	-	-	-	707 457	1 741 486	7 064 709
China	2 184 110	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2 927 326	5 111 436
Bangladesh	-	1 277 624	1 095 231	-	-	2 488 471	-	-	-	-	-	795 763	5 657 089
Pakistan	408 412	1 483 737	996 288	-	-	833 314	-	-	-	-	-	537 047	4 258 798
Ukraine	370 255	-	-	-	-	-	3 268 263	-	355 751	-	289 743	272 594	4 556 606
Philippines	2 061 178	644 828	564 769	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	919 850	4 190 625
Afghanistan	142 504	481 215	-	-	-	-	-	1 598 223	-	2 710 601	250 444	-	5 182 987
Total	18 743 328	7 213 002	5 827 588	3 792 505	3 330 586	3 321 785	3 268 263	3 195 357	2 831 769	2 710 601	2 466 741	10 279 767	66 981 292

Table 1 illustrates how many migrants from each of the 10 highest emigration developing countries move to which country. From the table, it is obvious that the largest group of emigrants is the transition from Mexico to the United States, equal to almost 10.9 million. Professors from the Center for Strategic and International Studies (CSIS) claim that the reason why Mexicans move to the United States is to upgrade their economic standing. There are some other factors, such as family ties in the destination city, but if financial prospects were more equal between the two countries, this factor would take precedence over family ties.

Discussion

Migration can change the people who move, the societies they move to, and even the societies they leave. For the same reason, migration can also become the most politically contentious issue, especially in societies where immigrants settle. As a result, when discussing migration, it is very easy to focus solely on the impact of immigration. However, we know that emigration can also have serious consequences, especially for some countries in the developing world. Therefore, an effective migration policy should go beyond local impacts and consider these mutual global impacts.

However, there is also reason to believe that migration itself can have a serious impact on economic development, especially in relatively poor countries experiencing a significant outflow of migrants. As the scale and complexity of migration flows have increased in recent years, researchers and policy makers are paying considerable attention to the mutual impact of flows of people, skills, knowledge, and remittances on development. However, there is also reason to believe that migration itself can have a serious impact on economic development, especially in relatively poor countries experiencing a significant outflow of migrants. As the scale and complexity of migration flows have increased in recent years, researchers and policy makers are paying considerable attention to the mutual impact of flows of people, skills, knowledge, and remittances on development.

Conclusion

This study analyzed the reasons, motives, and countries to which emigrants from developing countries prefer to move. Most people move from India to improve their quality of life, and emigrants from developing countries prefer to move to the US. The largest group of migrants is from Mexico to the United States.

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